

TECHNOLOGY AND NANOTECHNOLOGY IN SMART BUILDINGS

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Abstract

In the category of nanotechnology, what in the first place seems to be a friendly environment and energy saving, which is among the excellent human progress. The use of modern technologies, including nanotechnology in construction, can be effective in functional characteristics of architecture, including sustainability and safety issues. Nanotechnology has more durability due to the ability to transform the fundamental characteristics of materials and solving structural problems. Most importantly, most environmental sustainability, intelligent materials and structures and multi-functional materials and materials are allowed through this new technology. Nanotechnology is very effective in constructing and improving the quality of buildings, and its benefits can increase the quality of materials, saving energy consumption and, consequently, sustainable architecture and environmental sustainability. The purpose of this study was to investigate the position of nanotechnology in the building to enhance the quality of building materials and achieve sustainable architecture using a descriptive analytical approach. The achievements of this research can be introduced and examine the solutions of energy conservation in the building and achieving sustainable architecture in intelligent buildings using nanoscale materials and technology.

Keywords: Nanotechnology, Nano materials, sustainable architecture, environmental sustainability, energy.

1.introduction

Nanotechnology is a name that refers to a type of manufacturing technology. Homework is achieved when it comes to its name, which is the ability to build objects from atoms, and then the ability to reinstate materials with atomic precision (Fazeli et al, 2005).

Nanotechnology is not a new string, but it means a new approach in all disciplines. Nanotechnology provides a new perspective of the production of materials on a nanoscale with different nuclear properties and layout. The goal of nanotechnology is actually making objects, atoms. With an approach from the bottom to top, the approach that nature is millions of years (Bagheri and Kovanlu, 2012).

In the current world, it is time when the alarm is completed by the completion of oil and fossil reserves, finding new sources of low-cost energy and maintaining reserves and resources for future generations is the success of the nations in the lack of dependence on others. On the other hand, reducing environmental pollution, preventing manpower and reduced costs is one of the features that are defined for each project or successful and sustainable activity; By supplying the resources required for each activity to maintain natural and renewal resources for the next generation and reduce pollution and maintain biomass. (vejdanzadeh 2014).

The application of nanotechnology in architecture includes a wide range of materials and equipment, which aims to objective and implement the theories. Nanotechnology can improve construction conditions. Reduce the need to maintain and reduce the cost of maintenance. The result of this improvement will be: reducing the consumption of raw materials and energy, as well as reduced carbon dioxide emissions, maintain natural resources, dynamic economic resources, and as a result of further comfort (Hagh panah 2013).

Based on the purpose of technology and nanotechnology in the intelligent cities of the research method used in this paper, the applied research method and based on the properties of the subject of descriptive method have been selected. Since this, with a comprehensive definition of Nano, refer to the use of this technology in the fields of smart buildings and emphasizes the construction and sustainable architecture and mention examples of the application of nanotechnology in the architectural and building industry as a case and Expressing the benefits and disadvantages of using this technology are presented and the results are presented.

2. Introduction of nanotechnology

The term Nano is derived from the Greek word of Nanos and the dwarf means. The phrasal phrase is like other proofers that are at the beginning of measurement units such as seconds, sooths, etc. A nanometer means a billion meters or 10 angstroms (equal to the dimensions of the five atoms). (Golabchi, 2011, p. 23) Nanotechnology is not a new string, but it means a new approach in all disciplines. Nanotechnology provides a new perspective of the production of materials on a nanoscale with different nuclear properties and layout. The goal of nanotechnology is actually making objects, atoms. With an approach from the bottom to top,

the approach that nature is millions of years (Bagheri and Kovanlu, 2014). Nanotechnology reduces human need for scarce materials and, by reducing the aluminum, provides a healthier environment. For example, studies show that over the next 10 to 15 years, the brightness of the progress of nanotechnology reduces global energy consumption by up to 10%, saving \$ 100 billion annually, as well as reducing air pollution by 200 million tons of carbon. (Majidi, Hashemi 2018).

3. Nanotechnology history in building construction

About 400 BC, Democritus Greek philosopher, for the first time, the atomic word that means divisible in Greek means to describe the material particles. Hence, maybe he can be considered the father of technology and nanoscience. Greek Nano roots' 'nan' means dwarf (Majidi, Hashemi 2018). Among the many achievements of this technology, its application in the production, transfer, consumption and storage of energy is high performance, which creates a tremendous transformation in this area. (keramat azar Azar 2015). Especially in consumption of energy resources and ultimately achieve sustainable development (Majidi, Hashemi 2018).

4. Nanotechnology in architecture

The application of nanotechnology in architecture includes a wide range of materials and equipment, which aims to objective and implement theories that did not go to the practical arena. Nanotechnology makes us a step closer to having the desired features of our desires. Materials that have unique features and engineers separate from old aggregates, with numerous problems when using them in construction processes. Perhaps the most important help of nanotechnology in the field of materials and materials materials helped the consumption of raw materials and energy meters (Golabchi 2013).

We can divide nanotechnology in architecture to 2 groups.

4.1 Sponge architecture, which is the use of geometry and structural structure in different biodegradable architecture. Livetick architecture is such a way to design and build clear buildings. That design and construction of the building is clear that their plans and lines are inspired by natural forms.

4.2 Calculus and nano use in the fields of production and manufacturing materials and materials that can be placed in this group. Also, it should be considered a large amount of pancel architecture, which is about 3 billion years old from the planet's life and during this period he introduced its industry as creative and capable architecture (Leydecker, 2008, p. 85).

5. Nanotechnology and environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability has defined this: "utilization and exploitation of natural resources, as the current need of the world is fulfilled energy and does not endanger the needs of subsequent generations." Not only does an effective use of energy sources, but rising the life of the useful period of materials and materials, are important criteria for maintaining environmental sustainability. Appropriate exploitation of energy sources, while maintaining and protecting these resources, has always been a matter of many environmental and building engineers. (Dezfuli 2011). Still, most of the energy needed in the world is based on coal and oil. Two energy sources that cause the highest emission of greenhouse gas emissions. Of course, for decades, replacement sources such as wind energy, sun energy, biomass energy, nuclear energy, geothermic energy and energy of ocean waves, but to date, have not been able to succeed all and perfection for traditional resources and fueled Fossils out of the energy generation cycle. Hence, expectations of nanotechnology are high for nodding of environmental issues. Undoubtedly, nanotechnology, although it is at the beginning of the road, has caused positive changes in environmental sustainability in different areas. (Majidi, Hashemi 2018).

6. Nanotechnology in building

Nanotechnology is a dramatic advancement in various scientific and industrial areas, including the construction industry. This technology provides many opportunities to strengthen competition in the construction industry such as construction faster, more reliable, more sustainable and more cost-effective. Nanotechnology is used in almost all parts of the building including skeleton, facade, construction systems and interior design. The use of this technology in the building industry has produced high performance multi-purpose building materials and, while creating value added, has increased the durability and quality of building materials. This technology helps two directions to the building industry: first, optimization and improvement of existing technologies. Second, the presentation of a new group of technologies and practices that was not before the advent of nanotechnology (Hosseini, dehkordi 2015). Therefore, the benefits of using nanotechnology in the building industry include increasing the quality of materials, saving energy and, consequently, economic savings. Based on the results of the studies, in the 10 applications of nanotechnology in the development of the world, the building industry is in the eighth place. Therefore, the use of nanotechnology in the building industry is small in terms of the extent of the industry. Although today we are witnessing limited use of nano materials in the building, according to the capabilities of this emerging technology, it is expected that in the near future, we can see a significant increase in the use of nano materials in the building industry. Nanotechnology activities at the world are highly expanding, and nanotechnology has very important aspects that are difficult to coordinate without a strategy for research and development. The possibility of preparing suitable building materials to control energy in the building is possible by this technology. Other applications of these materials are also studied in building materials and building materials by the Institute of National Research Council for research on some construction materials including cement and glass (Majidi, Hashemi 2018).

- Use of nanoparticles, nanotubes and carbon nanotubes to improve the quality and sustainability of building materials as well as minimize pollution
- Build cheaper steel without corrosion
- Production of thermal insulation materials with very high performance
- Production of ultra-thin layers of self-cleaning and color change to reduce pollution and energy consumption
- Production of nano sensors and nano materials
- The ability to repair for more reliable buildings

Figure 1. Building with Nano structure(Wiki Pedia)

7. Appropriate achievement of civil engineers using nano materials

If we want to summarize the impact of nanotechnology on building materials and products, it can be said that nanotechnology allows us to upgrade the characteristics of materials. Engineers and civil engineers have turned to building building nanoparticles in order to increase the strength of the building and the performance of materials. Adding nanoparticles to materials such as metal, cement and concrete reinforces features such as heat resistance, tensile strength, cyclewrigance and self-esteem. On the other hand, the architectural profession and construction industry are faced with a huge range of materials and materials.

In fact, materials make up the core of the building and their impact on the environment cannot be ignored. Nano achievements in this field can be mentioned that reduces energy consumption and increases life. In general, nanotechnology with the efficiency of tools and materials used in different sectors, as well as reducing the consumption of raw and energy, has provided effective measures to protect natural and environmental resources, all of these

steps effective in The truth is the realization of sustainable design (Tanazian and sariangholi, 2013).

8.Achieve smart homes using Nano materials

Materials make up the central core of buildings and is huge in human strength. By investigating the processes of conventional materials and their performance in the long run, we conclude that materials and materials are gradually eroded and invasive agents of the external environment), such as sunlight and moisture (them to the abyss The deterioration can only be used by applying appropriate methods to increase the life of materials, which typically continues care procedures as long as they are worn out and replace new materials. This The method is still dominant on the construction process. If we want to summarize the effects of technology in a sentence, it can be said: " nanotechnology, technology that allows us and enabled us. It makes upgrade features or even create new features (Ashby 2009). Today, the combination of steels and resistive concrete in design of structures is widely used. These materials can improve the design and construction methods of buildings. For example, in the attitude of the design of the structures, they should satisfy a high level of environmental standards with emphasis on the cost of useful life period, often used for such materials, because these materials have a better nature with the environment. And also have recycling capabilities (Golabchi 2011).

9.explain Nano material in construction

9.1 Automatic coverage

This style of coatings into two groups

- hydrophobic
- Hydrophilicity

is divided into two types of coating due to the presence of water. Today, the maintenance of the building and its components, especially in the surfaces, are of great importance in the building view. Cleaning coatings are created in two forms of color on the surfaces, with the advantage of these colors, clean and significant reduction in maintenance, meaning that the number of cleaning per year and reducing the consumption of detergents and the cost of manpower, as well as reducing the amount of The depreciation of surfaces in the wash during the year decreases (Kolahdoz 2018).

Table 1: Automatic coverage

Nano materials	Application	Property
Anti-bacterial	Bath wall, kitchen, restaurant and bathroom	Eliminate microbial contamination in the environment
Antismoke	Restaurant, kitchen, corridors and ...	Lack of dust and dust in a closed space
Scratch resistant	Parking, Places	High wear resistance and friction
Waterproof	Kitchen, pool, bathroom	Prevent water penetration.
thermal resistance	The kitchen wall, near the flame and ..	Prevent the destruction of color film against heat
Self-cleaning	Wall halls, rooms and corridors	Failure to influence contamination inside the film of ease in cleaning

9.2 Insulation

Insulation and coating such as foam in the building plays a significant role in spending energy, and also creates comfort and relaxation of people living in a residential unit. (golkohi 2022).
Types of Insulation:

Sound, thermal, moisture is divided.

9.2.1 Sound insulation

The sound insulation in the building is used to reduce and cope with the face and transfer of audio contamination from the environment to another environment, which also reduces the velocity of sound waves in the sound of sound waves in this regard. Advantages that are as follows: High quality and higher ability to proportion to conventional insulations and requires less thickness. (Tabrizi 2021)

Figure 2. Sound insulation (Wikipedia)

9.2.2 thermal Insulation

An important factor in choosing these insulators is their thermal resistance. As much as this resistance is higher, the insulation passes the heat and saves itself, so instead of insulating thickness, their thermal resistance is better compared. The basis for insulating materials is based on a large number of cavities in the structure, which can hold the air as much as possible. Nano materials are more capable of trapping air in substance due to smaller and more nanoparticles. Thermal insulators are very resistant, lightweight and quality, and more than traditional insulators, more capable of reducing energy loss and have 2 to 6 times higher returns (Tabrizi 2021).

Figure 3. thermal Insulation (Wikipedia)

9.2.3 Moisture insulation

Moisture insulators are referred to in materials that can prevent water penetration. Moisture causes decay of materials and producing pathogens and harmful. Increased against the growth of bacteria, mushrooms, mildew and the influence of ultraviolet radiation (Tabrizi 2021).

Figure 4. Moisture insulation (Wikipedia)

9.3 Concrete

Annual production of concrete among other materials is the most, and probably why this material is with serious advances using nanotechnology. One of the most important aspects of the use of nanotechnology in concrete is probably cement hydration control, which can lead to the production of a new generation of products that can be more consistent. By adding SiO₂ nanoparticles (silica), cement-based materials can improve the durability and resistance of refined materials. In the case of corrosion problems in concrete products, nanotechnology can provide clever solutions and covers that respond to external influences and repair or prevent damage. The current research on the use of multi-purpose materials, nanoparticles and carbon nanotubes indicate that these materials increase the compressive strength of cement mortar samples significantly, but also changes their electrical properties that can be used to monitor the health and diagnosis of injury. (Ghorbani 2022).

Figure 5. concrete (Wikipedia)

9.4 Glasses

9.4.1 Smart glass

From Smart Glass capabilities, it is possible to change the amount of transparency and color of the glass, which can play an effective role in controlling the intensity of light and reducing energy losses, and thus reduces the intravenous entry into the environment and its destructive complications on the skin. Body and home appliances prevent the need for curtains and accessories in the building. (Mohsenipour, Ranjbar 2018).

Figure 6. Smart Glass (Wikipedia)

9.4.2 Anti-reflective glass

These glasses can be used for applications that need low light reflection and high passage. Museums, valuable objects, machines, glasses, mobile and These glasses are made up of nanotechnology in the construction industry. (Mohsenipour, Ranjbar 2018).

Figure 7. Anti-reflective glass (Wikipedia)

9.4.3 Anti-dust glass (self-cleaning)

In this glass, in addition to self-cleaning, there are materials that cause bacteria and infections. Also, using these glasses, it can always be clear and clean. (Mohsenipour, Ranjbar 2018)

Figure 8. Anti-dust glass self-cleaning (Wikipedia)

9.4.4 Anti-fire glass

Using anti-phase glass nanoparticles, which form a sponge coating, and prevent the glass breakthrough. These glasses versus typical glass 50% lighter and their anti-fire effect is 2 times more. (Mohsenipour, Ranjbar 2018).

Figure 9. Anti-fire glass (Wikipedia)

10. conclusion

The use of nano technology is used in almost all parts of the building, including skeleton, facade, construction systems and interior design. The use of nano technology in the building industry produces high quality building materials, as well as the durability and quality of construction materials. The expansion and development of nano technologies in the construction industry can lead to the production of high-function and functional products, therefore, is waiting for the progress of nanotechnology in Iran construction industry as one of the The largest platform of the country is converted to massive market production of nanoscale products. Informing the architects and building engineers, and the placement of units in universities and understanding the students of relevant disciplines can be useful programs for recognition and use of these materials in smart buildings.

References

- [1] A. Fazeli, M. Zarei, A. Akhavan, M. Moradi, M. Darab, A. Salimi, S. Seyedmostafavi, S. Alikhani, M. Farazkish, F. Moaied, F. Eslamipoor, S. Noroozi . Nanotechnology Mirror of Creation, (2005).
- [2] F. Bagheriand, S. Kiwanolo. Proposal of an inventive panel with concrete Ekliki in line with Buildings Buildings Second Internal Architectural Conference and Decoration of the High School Research Institute (2012).
- [3] L. Vejdanzadeh. Application of Nanotechnology in Architecture, Architecture and Urban Design Architecture and Winter No. 13. (2011).
- [4] M. Hagh panah, F. Deghani. New structures in intelligent buildings with sustainable architectural approach. National Conference on Sustainable Architecture and Urban Development.(2013)
- [5] M. Golabchi, K. Taghizade, E. Sorooshnia. Nanotechnology in Architecture & Construction Engineering, Tehran: University of Tehran, (2011).
- [6] F. Majidi, M. Hashemi,, A review of the position of technology and technology in achieving sustainable architecture, (2018).
- [7] S. Leydecker, Nano Materials in Architecture, Interior Architecture and Design, BirkhauserVerlag AG. (2008).
- [8] S. Keramat azar, A. Feyzollah Beigi, examining the status of intelligent materials and self-restoration in sustainable architecture. First National Conference on Architecture, Restoration, Urban Development and Sustainable. (2015).

[9] A. Gorji, Sustainable Architecture Solutions, along with Japan's architecture. Journal of Fine Arts, No. 41. (2010).

[10] M. Golabichi, Nanotechnology in Architecture and Building Engineering. Published University of Tehran, (2011).

[11] A. Dezfuli, Investigating the role of nanotechnology in the realization of sustainable architecture and energy saving. Proceedings of the second national architectural conference. (2011).

[12] L. Hosseini, M. Dehkordi, S. Hosseini, Sustainability in National Conference On New Theories in Architecture and Urbanism. (2015).

[13] SH.Tanazian, H. Sarbani, the effect of nanotechnology in sustainable architecture. Sustainable architectural conference and urban development. (2013)

[14] M.F. Ashby, P.J. Ferreira, D.L. Schodeck, Nanomaterials, Nanotechnologies & Design (an introduction for engineers & architects), 1st edition, Oxford ,UK, (2009).

[15] Z. Kolahdozan, Intelligent Structures and Nano-Technologies in the building, the second international conference on new research findings in civil engineering, architecture and urbanity. (2018).

[16] N. Golkohi, Impact of Nanotechnology in the Building Industry and Multifunctional and Multifunctional Design, 6 TH. National Congress on Civil Engineering, Architecture and Urban. (2022).

[17] A. Tabrizi, Application of Nanotechnology Materials in the Building Industry, International Conference on Civil, Architecture, Development and Reconstruction of Urban Infrastructure. (2021)

[18] S. GHorbani, the effect of nanotechnology and nano materials in improving the strength of concrete (with a specific look at nano silica), the 7th International Conference on Civil Engineering, Architecture and Urban Development. (2022).

[19] GH. Mohsenipour, M. Ranjbar, Nanotechnology Place in the preparation of self-cleaning glass for application in the building, 2nd International Conference of Civil Engineering, Architecture and Crisis Management. (2018).